

Weaving Before Electronics: A Spiral Design Process for Sound-Interface Making

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Figure 1: *Kirma*, a work-in-progress sound interface

Abstract

This paper reports the design and conceptualisation process of *Kirma*, a work-in-progress sound interface developed from Andean spiral temporality and the ancestral technique of coil basketry. The focus is on method rather than on a finished artefact, with design and process treated as integral to the artwork. This work promotes a practice-led, cosmotechnical approach in which gesture, material, and sound converge through situated making. Methodologically, it aligns with Technical Practice Research and proceeds through non-linear spiral iteration, where knowledge arises via cycles of weaving, listening, documentation and attention to material resistances. From this stance, the paper articulates a spiral design methodology that links Andean temporality with technical practice and craft, advances a material-ethical orientation grounded in proximity and gleaning, and situates the instrument as an interface that emerges from weaving before electronics. Taken together, these orientations support alternative modes of interaction and listening and point toward pluriversal directions for sound-interface design.

Keywords

Practice-led Research, Decolonial Aesthetics, Andean Spiral Temporality, Coil Basketry, Tangible Sound Interface

1 Introduction

Musical instrument design often embodies universalist assumptions about time, material, and interaction, privileging linear progress, efficiency, and control [19, 25, 30]. These paradigms can hide alternative technical genealogies in which technique is understood as a relational practice grounded in territory, care, and community [19, 25]. Within this context, reflecting on composition through circular time and Andean traditions foregrounds temporal models that emphasise return, continuity, and relational presence, which question linear design trajectories and invite a renewed understanding of musical creation as a cyclical and processual practice [4, 8].

Although NIME has demonstrated growing interest in non-linear temporalities, situated materialities, and the revival of ancestral technologies [8, 22, 35], few studies integrate these elements into a design process that remains accountable to cosmological perspectives outside universalist paradigms [4, 12, 13, 17, 23, 29, 44, 56]. This paper responds to this gap by approaching the development of *Kirma*¹ not as the construction of a finished

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¹The term *Kirma* comes from the linguistic and symbolic worldview of the Quimbaya-Kumba peoples. It refers to a vital balancing force that links humans to the sacred and sustains harmony among the different realms of the world [46].

instrument, but as an inquiry into practice, process, and emergent concepts.

Kirma, (Figure 1) is a tangible sound interface informed by coil basketry and Andean spiral temporality [8, 14, 20, 46]. As a work in progress, this study documents a design inquiry in which gesture, material, sound, and temporality co-emerge through weaving, listening [27], and situated experimentation [38, 45]. By not framing the interface as a final outcome, the design stage is brought to the foreground as an important artistic act in its own right. Throughout this paper, *Kirma* is not merely a showcase for a spiral design methodology. The instrument provides context for the method to unfold, acting as a catalyst and not simply an endpoint.

This orientation corresponds to practice-led research approaches [36, 38, 45] that consider technical processes, material negotiations, and conceptual developments as fundamental sites of knowledge production.

Kirma is conceived as an instrument in formation, with the spiral serving as a methodological, material, and sonic principle that moves beyond its role as a purely formal motif [4, 8]. This paper contributes a non-linear, spiral design methodology that connects Andean temporalities with technical practice and craft [4, 8, 47, 48] and situates the instrument's emergence within a cosmotechnical perspective [25, 26, 29].

In doing so, this article prioritises documenting the concepts, theory, and design practice that shape the instrument-building process by emphasising proximity, gleaning, and territorial responsibility [4, 56, 59], and by examining coil basketry as a technology of memory and gestural grammar [24, 37, 52].

Finally, adopting a spiral logic aligned with Technical Practice Research (TPR) [38], the work reflects on how knowledge emerges through making, returning, and attending to resistances and deviations as they unfold [45]. The learning of weaving, the engagement with local and gleaned materials, and the sustaining of practice within diasporic community spaces inform the evolving decisions about interaction and sound to be developed in subsequent stages [4, 19, 56].

From the perspective of sound-interface research, it is worth asking why *Kirma* is considered a Digital Musical Instrument, and why electronics and computation are incorporated beyond the woven object itself. Coil basketry already functions as a technology of memory and gestural grammar: it organises rhythm, friction, accumulation, and haptic knowledge through material practice. The structural logic of the coil as its turns, tactile relief, and accumulated gestures hold an interactive potential that precedes any electronic layer. Integrating capacitive sensing, microcontroller-based sound generation, and real-time mapping does not add technology to the basket; it activates and translates what is already latent in the woven spiral. In this way, circular motion becomes sustained sound not through imposition, but through correspondence. *Kirma* is situated within DMI design, yet ancestral material genealogies are not subordinated to dominant engineering models. The interface emerges from material practice, with computation extending what the weave already affords.

2 Positioning

This paper is written from the first author's position as an immigrant artist-researcher working from the Andean diaspora. I do not self-identify as Indigenous or as white; my standpoint

is *ch'ixi*² shaped by the coexistence of Andean heritage, migration, and contemporary technical practice in Bristol. While first-person reflections and design decisions arise from my own situated practice, the conceptual framing and methodological precision have been refined through ongoing dialogue and manuscript review with my co-authors and wider research community.

3 Background

In this work in progress, *Kirma*'s design has been oriented around three interrelated thematic areas: spiral temporalities and ritual listening; cosmotechnics and situated materiality; and technical practice and material agency. Together, these blocks aim to displace universalist assumptions about technology, situate design within specific cultural genealogies, and conceive the interface as a material-sound becoming in which knowledge emerges through practice.

3.1 Spiral temporalities and ritual listening

Stories go in circles. They don't go in straight lines. It helps if you listen in circles because there are stories inside and between stories, and finding your way through them is as easy and as hard as finding your way home. Part of finding is getting lost, and when you are lost you start to open up and listen.

Terry Tafoya [53].

Across many Indigenous traditions, time tends to be perceived cyclically; in Andean thought, this takes material form in practices that foreground continuity and the co-presence of past and future [9, 18, 47]. This temporality is not identical in each return; it is cyclical, or more precisely, spiral [21], as every turn meets a world that has been subtly or, at times, radically transformed. It unfolds through agricultural, cosmic, and ritual rhythms, operating through returns, renewals, and repetitions that accumulate experience across each spiral movement [51].

In the Quimbaya-Kumba tradition, this intuition is embodied by the coiled snake (*biri*), a guide teaching that moving forward requires honouring one's origins [20, 46]. This vision resonates with the Aymara concept of *qhip nayra* (Figure 2): walking into the future while facing the past. Here, the past lies before our eyes as a visible, known horizon, while the future remains at our backs, unseen and yet to be walked [47, 51, 60].

Drawing on an Indigenous HCI perspective [18], Whyte [61] proposes shifting "possible futures" toward a spiralling temporality in which ancestors and descendants coexist, challenging the dominant linearity of speculative design. Similarly, Krenak [28] argues that "if there is a future to imagine, it is ancestral, because it is already present," inviting us to inhabit time as a living and relational space.

This temporal horizon requires a corresponding mode of attention. Following Tim Ingold, sound is not an external object; it is a medium that *ensounds* the body and situates it in relation to its environment [27]. Read together with Tafoya's image of listening in circles [53], this would imply a ritual listening that privileges returns, layers, and continuities over discrete events or forward-driven metrics.

²Notion developed by Silvia Rivera Cusicanqui to describe identities and practices where heterogeneous and even contradictory elements coexist without merging into a single, homogeneous whole. The term evokes the Aymara idea of *jaspeado*, a speckled, variegated pattern to express a form of coexistence in which differences persist in tension, not blending or resolving into synthesis[48].

Figure 2: Diagram of the Aymara concept Qhip Nayra: Facing the known past while walking into the unseen future.

This stance also avoids treating non-linear temporalities as mere stylistic choices, instead recognising their epistemic depth and cultural specificity. Literature on decolonising HCI [30] warns of terminological, ethical, and micro-colonisation paradoxes, calling on us to enact temporal models that remain accountable to situated epistemologies and community continuities.

3.2 Cosmotechnics and situated materiality

The philosopher Yuk Hui calls the inseparability of technique, morality, and cosmos "cosmotechnics", pointing out that all technology emerges from a situated worldview. From this perspective, there is no universal "Technology"; what exists are multiple technical genealogies aligned with the cosmologies of each people [26, 29].

This notion challenges modern instrumental universalism and opens the possibility of validating epistemologies and techniques that emerge from alternative genealogies, beyond dominant rationalist paradigms, as legitimate sources of contemporary design. This is consistent with Escobar's idea of *transition design* [19], seeking to shift interface design away from the hegemony of linear efficiency towards a technical pluriversity that validates other forms of knowledge. In the context of NIME, this is linked to technodiversity [25], understood as the coexistence of different lineages of instrumental construction, material, gestural, and sonic, free from subordination to hegemonic canons of engineering or usability. Examples such as *Gambiarra*³ in Brazil demonstrate situated cosmotechnics based on improvisation, repair, and recombination [56].

In parallel, taking up Argabrite et al.'s assertion [4] that *technology is land*⁴ foregrounds the genealogies of matter including its extraction, refinement, assembly, and waste, and shifts design ethics from a focus on product functionality to one centered on material continuity, repair, reuse, and the exposure of otherwise opaque supply chains. Within this ethical horizon, materials are not neutral substrates, because they signify histories, territorial relations, and economies of care.

³Brazilian practice of improvised technical creativity that repurposes available or discarded materials through situated, ingenious, and non-conventional solutions[56].

⁴"Technology is land" is a theoretical perspective that understands electronic devices not as abstract objects, but as the earth itself fragmented and transformed through processes of resource extraction, manufacturing, and disposal. This lens foregrounds the colonial and capitalist dynamics embedded in technology, shifting the focus from economic ownership to stewardship of the ancient materials and territories from which these devices are derived.[4].

3.3 Situated Technical Practice and Material Agency

Following Hui, technique goes beyond being a mere functional means; it expresses how a culture understands life and the cosmos [24, 29]. Along these lines, TPR conceives technical practice as a place where knowledge is produced through real-time documentation, reflexivity, and attention to differences in the process [38].

By shifting focus away from the final artefact, this approach recognises that decisions, errors, materials, limits, and affections shape the instrument as it evolves. This is in line with Science and Technology Studies (STS) [38] perspectives and Andean epistemologies, such as Silvia Rivera Cusicanqui's *ch'ixi* notion, which permits the coexistence of heterogeneous logics without reducing them to a homogeneous synthesis [48].

Similarly, for Pickering [39], technical-scientific practice is a "mangle" or dance of agencies that frames design as a negotiation with resisting and affording matter. In addition to being shaped, materials react, offer resistance, and suggest new possibilities; design unfolds by attending and adapting to these responses. The instrument is therefore co-constituted with its materials and contexts, with the process characterised by iteration and responsiveness, in contrast to linearity.

These conceptual foundations inform the practical and historical analysis that follows. The next section reviews related NIME work on circular interfaces, ancestral technologies, and coil basketry.

4 State of the art

Recent NIME work demonstrates how media archaeology and design fiction can reveal the ethical imaginaries embedded in historical instruments and mobilise them toward speculative futures [22]. In contrast, this study adopts a situated decolonial stance, prioritising accountability to ancestral, material and communal continuities as opposed to speculation detached from lived conditions [19, 28, 30]. This section reviews circular interfaces, culturally-situated DMIs, and coil basketry as a technological foundation.

4.1 Tactile and circular interfaces

From a formal perspective, the circular representation of time has been explored in NIME as an alternative to the linearity dominant in DAWs, sequencers, and standard notation. *Cycle* [8] is a direct reference; it organises events in a circular timeline to question the notion of homogeneous time, proposing forms of perception in which the immediate past and the imminence of return coexist. This logic enables compositional decisions that dialogue with bodily rhythms and natural cycles, demonstrating that the way time is represented directly influences the performer's gestures.

Other related musical interfaces came from early tools such as Trueman's *Cyclotron* [57] to algorithmic systems like *XronoMorph*, which use circular geometries to articulate non-linear rhythmic structures [34]. Although these proposals expand the exploration of circular time, few explicitly integrate specific cultural temporalities or dialogue with textile materialities or vernacular techniques. Beyond HCI, recent philosophical work articulates spiral temporality as a culturally specific alternative to linear and cyclical models [21].

4.2 Ancestral technologies, cultural cosmologies, and situated materialities

Within our field, there is a growing interest in reviving ancestral technologies through contemporary means. Instead of attempting to replicate historical objects, these works seek to reactivate ways of thinking that can shape new models of interaction rooted in situated cultural structures [25].

4.2.1 Own background at NIME: *Kirma* is part of a line of interfaces based on pre-colonial Andean technologies I previously developed, the *Electronic_Khipu* [12] and the *Kanchay_Yupana* [13], in which I reactivated the khipu and the yupana⁵ as sound interfaces that interrelate memory, calculation, and gesture to challenge established frameworks of representation and control rooted in universalist assumptions. These works demonstrate that historically erased technologies can serve as epistemologies for contemporary sound interface design [35].

4.2.2 Time as the axis of cultural design: The *O-* instrument, [44] examines how different cultural conceptions of time can be materially inscribed in a DMI. Its design combines a circular board, often associated with philosophies centred on recurrence, and a linear one, linked to modern paradigms of progress. The instrument functions as an epistemological tool that demonstrates how the temporal models incorporated into the design influence listening, interaction and composition.

4.2.3 Politics of materiality: *BRAIDS_*: [2] offers an essential scheme to comprehend the political and cultural dimensions of materials in the design of sound instruments. Based on the Black American tradition of hair braiding, it uses woven strands as a compositional structure, showing that ancestral materials have aesthetic, historical, and political agency. Through diffractive methodologies⁶, the project demonstrates that DMIs embody values and memories, and that choosing a material is always an ethical decision.

4.2.4 Cosmotronics situated in DMIs: The *Zhu Nao* [29] is a bamboo-based instrument designed through the lens of Chinese cosmotronics and serves as a strong example of situated design. The instrument embodies a specific cosmology through its material selection, handcrafted construction, and relationship with the environment. Beyond aesthetics, it integrates rhythms and modes of interaction that reflect ways of thinking emphasising continuity, process, and natural harmony.

4.3 Affinities with Latin American sound ritual-technological practices

A significant group of Latin American artists has drawn inspiration from ancestral technologies, ritual textiles, and indigenous knowledge systems for their work with sound and interface design. I highlight a few representative examples below.

- **Paola Torres Núñez del Prado.** In addition to her reactivations of the Andean khipu, such as the *ML:knot()* or the *Hanap Pacha Khipu*, she transforms a loom into the

Sincreto Loom Biosynth, where weaving and biosensors generate sound together [54, 55].

- **Constanza Piña** also reimagines the khipu as *Khipu Electrotextile Pre-Hispanic Computer*, emphasising the cosmic and spectral dimension of textiles [40].
- **Juan C. Duarte Regino**, with *AUGURY*, explores divination practices through a multi-channel device guided by environmental data, positioning the interface as a ritual artefact [17].
- **Moisés Horta Valenzuela (*Hexorcismos*)** uses the Mesoamerican maize-throwing divination tradition (Mook pajk wëjwë) with *SEMILLA AI*, an interface that navigates the latent space of a neural audio model (RAVE), aligning ritual contingency with neural synthesis [23].
- **Sandra de Berduccy (*aruma*)** turns Andean weaving into a haptic-sonic interface in works such as *JIWASANAKA* and *AWAY I TAKIY*, she interlaces natural fibres with copper/conductive elements so that touch and proximity generate data and sound [16].

4.4 Coil basketry as a technology of memory

Coil basketry, a central technique in *Kirma*, is an ancient technology found in different regions around the world. Its transcontinental presence suggests a convergence around the coil as a form of accumulation, containment, continuity, and care [24, 31, 43].

In North America, baskets from peoples such as the Chumash codify histories and cosmologies in addition to serving practical purposes [24]. In Colombia, Guacamayas' coil basketry (Figure 3) transmits community knowledge through repetition and variation [50, 52]. It is also one of the main artefacts crafted by the Sikuani, Curripaco, Puinave, and Yeral ethnic groups in the Orinoquia and Amazonian territories, where, beyond being an economic activity, it serves as a means of connection to their ancestors and a fundamental tool for their daily survival [10, 15]. In West Africa and the Afro-descendant diaspora, fanner baskets used for rice embody ecological knowledge, agricultural memory, and cultural resistance [37].

In the Andean context, basketry like other precolonial technologies such as the khipu and the yupana, articulates touch, rhythmic repetition, and memory, shaping a manual grammar that organises gesture, time, and object.

From this perspective, adding electronics to a basket does not constitute bringing technology into the object; it activates a dialogue with an ancestral technology that is already present. The coil not only supports sound interaction but also constitutes the very epistemology of the instrument. The integration of structural logic, sensors, and frictional interaction positions *Kirma* within research that embraces materials as partners in design, placing the woven spiral at the temporal, material, and conceptual foundation of the instrument.

Taken together, these examples situate *Kirma* within a broader field of culturally-informed DMIs while highlighting the lack of approaches where weaving itself becomes the design method. The next section details the methodology through which *Kirma* emerges.

5 Designing Through Weaving: A Spiral Approach

5.1 Making *Kirma*

Kirma is conceived as a tactile sound instrument based on the spiral logic of Andean temporality and the technique of coil

⁵A khipu and a yupana are ancestral Andean knowledge technologies: the khipu, a system of knotted cords used to encode and transmit information through tactile and numerical patterns, and the yupana, a grid-based calculating device that enabled complex arithmetic through the spatial placement of counters.

⁶Diffractive methodologies move beyond reflective representation to focus on patterns of interference. By reading practices, software, and materials through one another, they trace how these elements co-produce emergent meanings and "cuts" in reality, rather than seeking linear cause-effect correspondences [7].

Figure 3: Guacamayas Coil Basket

basketry. Its structure is proposed to be a flat basket composed of seven turns or coils, each approximately 1.5 cm thick, to afford gestural precision and appropriate haptics. The weave of natural fibres constitutes the gestural topology of the interface, while capacitive sensors, mapped to real-time synthesis processes via an integrated microcontroller, will be arranged on each coil.

The basket will be mounted on a 3D-printed base designed to house the wiring and electronic components without interfering with the ergonomics or tactile reading of the fibres. Unlike my previous interfaces, conceived as performance-oriented MIDI controllers, I am designing *Kirma* as a stand-alone, plug-and-play device based on an embedded microcontroller, so that no external computer is required during performance. This approach is guided by a set of core principles that are iteratively refined through hands-on practice, particularly as I learn how the absence of a computer in performance more readily supports the situated and ritualistic nature of my work.

More than a finished object, I approach *Kirma* as an ongoing process in which technical, material and conceptual decisions are intertwined. Its design emerges from the practice of weaving, from gathering local materials and from listening that precedes electronics. In this sense, the instrument currently exists as a material prototype and as a cosmotechnical gesture that guides the subsequent development of electronics, synthesis and interaction.

In this context, the digital layer does not add extra functionality but operates as a form of translation, making audible what the weave already organises through space and gesture. The integration of capacitive sensing and computation does not overwrite the basket's logic, but extends it, allowing the accumulated gestures inscribed in the coil to be articulated sonically.

Framed in this way, *Kirma* can be understood as a DMI situated within technodiversity [26], without subordinating non-hegemonic material genealogies to dominant engineering models. Rather than beginning with what digital technology can enable and seeking an appropriate material support, the interface emerges from material practices grounded in ancestral techniques. In this process, computation follows the weave: it supports, amplifies, and translates the affordances already present in the spiral structure.

Figure 4: Spiral conception process of *kirma*

5.2 Genealogy of a living spiral

The origin of *Kirma* lies in a series of material and affective encounters that took place during a period of transition between projects. During a visit to the UCLA Fowler Museum, I came across a coil basket from Botswana. Its density, its way of containing movement, and the way it organised space generated a deep resonance which remained latent for years.

This material recognition was retrospectively linked to my previous practice in *Spiral* [11], a performance that explored cycled temporality, the Aymara time conception of *qhip nayra*, and the notion of ancestral future. In that work, circular listening functioned as a ritual, opening a mode of composition based on return and temporal simultaneity. The experience with the basket revealed that this same spiral could also be woven as an instrument, marking a shift from a performative gesture to a tangible, cumulative form of time. Notably, a couple of years later, I premiered the performance *Spiral* in the very same space where I first encountered the coil basket at the Fowler Museum. This connection between place and practice exemplifies the cyclical pattern that shapes my research (Figure 4).

Since then, the central question is no longer “how to design a circular instrument?” Instead, it asks “what happens when an instrument is born from a spiral that was already active in my embodied, sonic, and cosmological practice?” *Kirma* thus emerges as a continuity of a form already present in the body and in listening, now finding its material support and technical expression through weaving.

5.3 Spiral (non-linear) design methodology

While the spiral informs both the design methodology and the emerging instrument, this section focuses on its function as a research and development logic, not merely as a formal or symbolic feature of *Kirma*.

Kirma's design methodology is articulated through the non-linear logic of the spiral, aligning iterative movements of return, review, and overlap with the Andean temporal conception of *qhip*

nayra explained in the figure 2. Instead of following a sequential pipeline (problem → prototype → test), development unfolds through spiral cycles, with earlier decisions remaining present and deviations serving as material for further iteration. This approach matches the project's conceptual framework and the logic of coil basketry, which organises gesture, time, and accumulation, and recognises that knowledge arises within the making process, not prior to or outside of it.

Although spiral and iterative models of knowledge production have appeared in various disciplines, they are typically framed as paths toward refinement and closure, with each cycle seen as progress toward a finished result. In contrast, *Kirma*'s spiral logic is not oriented toward closure but toward accumulation and coexistence. Each turn of the coil contains those that came before, materially and temporally. This is not just a formal difference; it reflects the epistemic logic of *qhip nayra*, where returning does not mean going backwards and incompleteness is not a failure, but the condition from which situated knowledge continues to emerge.

The methodological approach is structured around the following principles:

- **Non-linear iteration:** Each technical, material or formal decision is revisited as the weaving progresses, keeping the process open and avoiding premature closures. The spiral allows a return to previous stages without cancelling them out, accumulating deviations and discoveries [45].
- **Practice as knowledge:** In line with TPR [38], real-time documentation records resistances, affections, errors, and findings that guide subsequent iterations. The emphasis is on cultivating situated understanding, not on pursuing linear optimisation.
- **Listen to the material:** Before integrating electronics, the fibre is explored through touch and friction. The density, torsion, and continuity of the coil operate as sound vectors, directing future interaction and possible mappings.
- **Situated temporality:** Technical decisions are understood as gestures inserted into a continuity in which past and future coexist in the present of doing. This orientation takes up the *qhip nayra* logic without re-explaining it, integrating it into the material process.
- **Community fabric:** The process is supported by spaces for co-learning with like-minded collectives, where material criteria are shared, techniques are contrasted, and the process is sustained affectively. These co-learning sessions function as return–review checkpoints: peers observe material decisions, suggest adjustments, and help sustain the temporal continuity required by the coil. In this way, community practice reinforces the spiral's logic of returning, sharing, and transforming.

Taken together, these principles articulate a practice-led, TPR-aligned methodology that supports a flexible, responsive process in which material negotiation, situated learning, and iterative documentation co-produce both the instrument and its emergent concepts. Within this spiral framework, error becomes material for experimentation, and design is treated not as a preparatory phase but as a core artistic act grounded in proximity, gleaning, and the temporal density of the coil. In this way, *Kirma* emerges from ongoing cycles of situated practice, return, and listening, in accordance with the technical genealogies that inspire it.

5.4 Sound conception

From an ecological perspective on hearing, and following Ingold [27], sound is understood not as an object, but as an enveloping medium situating the body in its environment. In *Kirma*, listening precedes electronics; it begins with the rubbing of fibres, repetition of gesture, and cumulative iteration of the coil.

The instrument is designed so that a circular gesture continuously generates and modulates sound. Sustained friction instruments such as singing bowls and the glass harp, referenced here for their circular tactile interaction, inform *Kirma*'s gestural logic. Unlike these high-register references, each turn of the coil is assigned a tone from the Andean pentatonic scale⁷ placed in the sub-bass range. The finger's pressure, speed, and trajectory on the woven surface activate and sustain continuous sound states, reinforcing the unbroken quality of the spiral.

Interaction evokes a ritual experience of listening, accompanying the repetition of gesture and allowing the sound to unfold slowly, without sudden breaks. Like my previous instruments [12, 13], *Kirma* is intended for live performance. Since performance in my practice often takes a ritual form, this instrument is conceived as a standalone device supporting continuity of gesture and attentive listening. As I listen to the pre-electronic woven surface, the friction of the fibres, their density, and the continuous spiral gesture inform the emerging sonic conception. Opting not to structure the instrument around sample playback, I explore friction-based and resonant synthesis models that sustain and modulate continuous sound states reflecting the hand's circular motion. Gesture, matter, and sonority influence one another, producing a resonant field and reinforcing relational listening aligned with the instrument's ritual nature.

The spectral architecture of *Kirma* grounds this relational conception in bodily perception. Frequencies assigned to each coil region are placed in the extreme sub-bass, near the threshold of hearing, so sound is first encountered as vibration before becoming pitch. These frequencies activate the body as a resonant structure, producing a palpable, enveloping sensation that precedes analytical listening. What is heard is always mediated by bodily resonance, dissolving boundaries between listener, performer, and medium.

This spectral logic is intertwined with the spatial organisation of the coil. The innermost turns concentrate denser harmonic activity, generating a saturated sonic field. As the gesture moves outward, the sound opens and thins, becoming less dense. This distribution articulates a temporal topography: moving inward returns to accumulation and weight, while moving outward opens toward continuity and dispersal.

The instrument's response preserves this continuity at the pitch level. As the finger traces the spiral, capacitive mapping generates frequencies that glide continuously without resolving into fixed tonal positions; there are no discrete notes, only uninterrupted movement between zones. Contact, pressure, and overlapping touch shape a sound that shifts without interruption. In this way, the trajectory between states becomes the primary unit of musical meaning, with motion taking precedence over arrival at a particular note. *Kirma* sustains sound as movement,

⁷The Andean pentatonic scale and its modes are documented across South American traditions by Aretz[3]. Mendivil [33] shows that a unified "Incan" pentatonic music was largely constructed by early twentieth-century musicologists, not based exclusively on empirical evidence. In *Kirma*, this scale is used as a personal artistic choice shaped by my connection to Andean music from the diaspora, serving as an expression of that relationship, not an exact cultural representation.

extending the same logic of continuity, duration, and return that structures both the woven coil and its design process.

5.5 Learning to weave a coil basket

I incorporate the experiential learning process of coil basketry as an epistemic way of understanding an ancestral technology through its manual practice. More than a preliminary step to design, weaving constitutes a space where technique, materiality and gesture simultaneously produce knowledge. This approach is in accordance with the principle outlined by Chilean artist Constanza Piña, which holds that the best way to understand an ancestral technology is to practise it in its procedural and material dimensions [41].

Traditionally, the coil baskets are constructed from a core of fibres, such as straw, grass, rope, strips of leaf, or other local materials, rolled from a small centre. Each turn is joined to the previous one by a thinner secondary fibre (such as raffia, fique, cotton, or tendons), which sews the spiral while allowing control of tension, density, and growth. The weaving progresses simultaneously outward (surface) and upward (edge), generating a cumulative topology in which small variations in thickness or twist produce differentiated haptic reliefs [5, 15, 24, 37, 42].

Shaped by my diasporic situation, my learning process has relied primarily on publicly available video resources from the Guacamayas Artisans Association and other basket-weaving tutorials on YouTube [1, 5, 6, 32, 58], as well as on consulting related publications from *Artesanías de Colombia*⁸ [49, 50], and on iterative, self-directed practice. While I cannot undertake an extended in-territory apprenticeship, these sources have allowed me to engage with the technique materially, reflexively, and respectfully in my current context.

Learning this technique through practice enables design decisions to emerge from the coil's grammar. The reliefs, imperfections, tensions, and rhythms of the stitch are more than formal details; they function as structural conditions that shape gestuality, friction, and potential modes of sonic interaction. In this way, the weave ceases to be a support and becomes the first instance of design; it configures the surface that will later dialogue with capacitive sensors, synthesis and performativity.

In *Kirma*, learning coil basketry centres less on perfecting a traditional technique and more on understanding its underlying principles so they can be applied within a contemporary, situated practice. Weaving, practised in continuity with its artisanal genealogies, operates as a space for observation, adjustment and material listening that underpins the development of the instrument.

5.6 Situated learning and initial iterations

An initial transfer of knowledge occurred during my meetings with the *Latinas in Bristol* (LIB)⁹ collective, where they taught me a basic crochet pattern, that enables me to understand the structural logic of coil weaving. Although this variant was not compatible with the haptic and structural requirements of *Kirma*, it provided fundamental lessons on how to control the centre, tension and pattern reading, essential elements for subsequently

addressing the winding and sewing technique characteristic of the coil.

From this preliminary basis, I turned to coil basketry in Guacamayas (Figure 3). This reference provided a useful technical and cultural model for evaluating stitch regularity, thickness control, and shape stability. Although the coil technique is used across multiple territories, the choice of this particular tradition enabled calibration of haptic and structural criteria relevant to the interface, especially in relation to the circular gesture and tactile legibility required by *Kirma*.

These early iterations revealed that small variations in tension, density, or twist considerably change the surface and, therefore, the possible modes of interaction. The process highlighted how weaving and design co-emerge, with the technique forming part of the instrument's very conception. In this phase, I learned the material conditions that would later guide the integration of electronics, sensors, and sound mapping.

Taken together, these situated experiences lay the foundations for further development, articulating community practice, traditional technique and material experimentation as inseparable elements of *Kirma's* design process.

5.7 Making a basket "away from the basket"

In its traditional context, coil basketry is made with local natural materials. In the Guacamayas case, for example, artisans work with a rolled white straw core covered with dyed fique, practices that articulate territory, material availability and community continuity [5, 32, 49, 50]. In the process of conceiving *Kirma* from Bristol (Bridge Studios, UWE)¹⁰, working "away from the basket" meant transferring this logic of proximity to a different territory, asking what local materials I could adopt without breaking the ethical and technical consistency of the project.

Under this principle of proximity materiality, I initiated a systematic exploration of fibres accessible in the immediate environment. This process included identifying available resources, evaluating their physical features, and determining their compatibility with the coil's logic. In place of replicating traditional materials, which would decontextualise the gesture, the approach sought to recognise what the present territory offers and how its materials can dialogue with an ancestral technique without replacing it.

Working far from the territory of origin did not mean reproducing the original basket; instead, it meant understanding the technique well enough to allow the new territory to intervene in the process. Geographical distance thus became a methodological condition, like a driving force that compels us to listen to what is available, reinterpret artisanal criteria, and allow *Kirma* to take shape from a convergence between technique, environment, and gesture.

5.8 Gleaning materials

In her documentary *Les glaneurs et la glaneuse* [59], the filmmaker Agnès Varda recovers the ancestral practice of gleaning, or collecting what is available and discarded, to reintegrate it into cycles of use. This gesture, more than an economy of survival, exposes the value logic of late capitalism and reopens the question of the links between territory, resources, and care. As a situated material strategy, gleaning is consistent with a *technology is land*

⁸*Artesanías de Colombia* is a government-linked corporation dedicated to the promotion, development, and preservation of Colombia's traditional and modern handicrafts sector.

⁹*Latinas in Bristol* is a community organisation that supports Latin American women in Bristol through cultural connection, wellbeing initiatives, and arts-based activities. <https://latinasinbristol.com/>

¹⁰<https://www.uwe.ac.uk/research/centres-and-groups/cate-research-overview/the-bridge-studios>

Figure 5: Meadow grass and 3D printing discarded fibres

ethic [4] and enables local conditions of scarcity or surplus to actively inform technical processes.

In the context of *Kirma*, I used gleaning to guide my initial search for local fibres suitable as the coil's core. My first exploration was focused on meadow grass (Figure 5) found in the gardens adjacent to my workspace at the Bridge Studios (UWE). After authorised collection, flexibility, and traction testing, I determined that this variety did not maintain the continuity required for stable winding, resulting in breaks and loss of torsion. Although functionally discarded, this trial provided a better appreciation of the structural requirements of the technique.

The search then shifted to the surrounding workshops, where thin plastic threads from 3D-printing waste (Figures 5 and 6), such as calibration strands, failed prints, and offcuts, were readily available. These residues offered the elasticity, continuity, and torsion control that natural fibres lacked, and their consistent presence made it possible to classify thicknesses, standardise lengths, and establish a reliable material flow for subsequent iterations of the weave.

Once the core was defined, I selected raffia as the secondary fibre for sewing and covering, due to its strength, tensile capacity, haptic legibility, and widely documented use in various coil basketry traditions [37]. The combination of a gleaned core and raffia (Figure 6) allows fine control of stitch density, growth angle, and relief, creating a surface suitable for frictional interaction and the subsequent integration of capacitive sensors.

By adopting gleaning, I inscribe the instrument in a policy of proximity, repair, and reuse. *Kirma* is nourished by failures and by materials that lie beyond conventional production chains, undoing the linear logic of production–consumption–disposal and enabling the human, environmental, and technical territory at hand to co-shape the instrument's final form [4, 56].

6 Results

6.1 Current status

The development of *Kirma* is currently in the material design phase. I am focused on crafting the first basket (Figure 1) and

Figure 6: Gleaned 3D printing threads used as the coil's core.

consolidating the instrument's conceptual design. Following the adopted processual methodology, the project moves away from the pursuit of a finished object toward a deeper understanding of how time, body, territory, and materiality shape the technique and guide each decision.

At this stage, I am weaving a structure that will shape the instrument (Figure 7). Each stitch of the coil simultaneously defines the physical stability, tactile legibility, and gestural possibilities that will eventually inform the sound interaction. The weave thus functions as the instrument's first interface. It is a surface that organises rhythm, manual tempo, and friction density.

Although the physical craft of the basket is an individual act, I have been developing the work embedded in the community dynamics of the *Latinas in Bristol* (LIB) collective. Following Arturo Escobar's framework on autonomy and the communal [19], *Kirma's* weaving emerges from a diasporic proximity that provides emotional and technical scaffolding, avoiding isolated production.

The weekly sessions at LIB function as a space for mutual observation and conversation, where the patience and temporal continuity required by the coil are sustained through collective presence.

These meetings act as iterative reviews in which feedback on stitch density, relief, and haptic zones feeds directly into subsequent weaving cycles. This social rhythm mirrors the spiral method, as return and review occur collectively, not in isolation, and reflects basketry as a technology of memory shared across bodies and time.

By weaving in company, the instrument's design goes beyond the strictly functional, integrating the relational and affective dimensions essential for autonomous design [19]. This community foundation will remain a structural axis in the upcoming phases, including sensor integration and the first performative explorations.

7 Conclusions

This paper has presented *Kirma* as a sound interface in progress, approached through weaving as a site of knowledge rather than electronics as a starting point. By recognising coil basketry as a technology of memory, the project situates instrument design within ancestral practices in which touch, repetition, and continuity organise gesture and knowledge [15, 24]. These practices precede and exceed any digital layer added to the object.

Figure 7: *Kirma* coil basket weaving process

Kirma is positioned as emerging from an Andean circular temporality, where the spiral articulates cosmologies that foreground return, relational presence, and the simultaneity of past and future, situating the project within Andean and Indigenous understandings of cyclical time [9, 20, 21, 47, 60]. While this paper introduces the concept of spiral temporality, a fuller engagement with the anthropological literature on the subject lies beyond its current scope and will guide the next stages of the research.

Here, the spiral is not merely a metaphor; it shapes the design methodology itself: non-linear, cumulative, and oriented toward return rather than closure. This work extends Pelinski et al.'s Technical Practice Research [38] through an artist-led, diasporic stance in which process documentation, material agency, and situated learning define where design happens, not just methods applied to it [36, 45]. Throughout this process, I have negotiated with material agency, understanding technics not as the imposition of form onto passive matter, but as co-emergence with materials that both resist and propose [39]. From a cosmotechnical perspective, computation follows the weave; the digital layer does not overwrite the basket's logic but translates what is already latent in the spiral [26].

Running through the process is an ethics of proximity and gleaning. The choice of local materials, such as discarded 3D-printing threads, traces territorial genealogies and rejects linear production logic. This resonates with decolonial design perspectives that foreground land-based technics [4], gleaning as a situated practice [59], and vernacular improvisation within technodiverse making [56].

These orientations constitute a spiral design methodology grounded in Andean temporality and the structural logic of the coil. By centring care, continuity, and relational density over optimisation, the work advances pluriversal directions for sound-interface design within NIME [19, 25].

Kirma remains unfinished by design. As an interface that continues to emerge through cycles of making, listening, and situated return, it holds that incompleteness is not a shortcoming but the condition from which situated knowledge continues to grow.

8 Ethical Standards

The paper aligns with the NIME code of ethics, emphasising territorial responsibility, respectful engagement with ancestral knowledge, and situated material practices.

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